

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT: CAMPHOR

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The dielectric constant and density of concentrated solutions of camphor in benzene have been measured over a range of temperature. The literature data for the dielectric constant of liquid and solid camphor have been recalculated by applying the new equation. The new moment in liquid state and in solution indicates an increased freedom of rotation whereby $2f + 1 = 2$ ($1kT$) increases to $2f + 1 = 3$ ($1.5kT$). The moments, thus increased, compare well with the moment in the solid state and also with the theoretical value for the moment of the molecule.

The moment of camphor in solid state has been calculated over a range of temperature by applying the new equation. The dielectric constant data and the density data for the purpose were taken from Yager and Morgan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2071) and White and Morgan (*ibid.* 1935, 57, 2078) respectively.

Higashi (*Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res., Tokyo*, 1932, 11, 729), Donle and Volkert (*Z. physical. Chem.*, 1936, **B8**, 60) and Wolf (*Physikal. Z.*, 1930, 31, 227) have measured the dipole moment of camphor in dilute solution.

In the present work the dielectric constant and density of camphor in benzene solution have been measured over a range of temperature and at various concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiophene-free benzene was made in the same way as in the preceding paper (this issue, p. 1). Camphor was purified by sublimation, m.p. 176° (lit. m.p. $176.3-176.5^\circ$).

TABLE I
Camphor.(a) Solvent: benzene. $P_2 = 180.0$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
	$w_2 = 0.2352$ ($f_2 = 0.1363$).				$w_2 = 0.2960$ ($f_2 = 0.1775$).			
25°	3.888	0.8816	1377	2.55	4.302	0.8864	1374	2.55
30°	3.868	0.8766	1375	2.57	4.278	0.8814	1370	2.56
35°	3.841	0.8716	1368	2.58	4.250	0.8764	1365	2.58
40°	3.819	0.8666	1363	2.60	4.228	0.8712	1363	2.60
45°	3.793	0.8616	1356	2.61	4.199	0.8662	1357	2.61
50°	3.771	0.8566	1352	2.63	4.171	0.8610	1352	2.63
	$w_2 = 0.3950$ ($f_2 = 0.2511$).				$w_2 = 0.4771$ ($f_2 = 0.3188$).			
25°	5.142	0.8920	1440	2.62	5.775	0.8988	1445	2.62
30°	5.139	0.8868	1450	2.64	5.714	0.8940	1432	2.63
35°	5.007	0.8816	1403	2.62	5.652	0.8892	1416	2.64
40°	4.933	0.8766	1380	2.62	5.584	0.8844	1404	2.64
45°	4.861	0.8714	1358	2.61	5.520	0.8796	1390	2.55
50°	4.793	0.8664	1338	2.61	5.459	0.8748	1376	2.66
	$w_3 = 0.6604$ ($f_2 = 0.4995$).							
30°	7.328	0.9126	1480	2.68				
35°	7.214	0.9080	1460	2.68				
40°	7.106	0.9035	1440	2.68				
45°	7.018	0.8990	1426	2.69				
50°	6.933	0.8944	1312	2.70				

$\mu_p - 25^\circ - 2.95$; $30^\circ - 2.93$; $35^\circ - 2.89$; $40^\circ - 2.90$; $45^\circ - 2.90$; $50^\circ - 2.89$.

TABLE II*

Solid

Temp.	ϵ .	d .	P .	μ_{new} .	Temp.	ϵ .	d .	P .	μ_{new} .
-80°	2.82	1.089	254.0	(0.50)	0°	12.7	1.002	1774.0	2.82
-79°	2.82	1.089	254.0	(0.50)	10°	12.2	1.001	1700.0	2.80
-55°	2.82	1.086	254.8	(0.55)	22°	11.7	1.000	1627.0	2.79
-45°	2.82	1.085	255.0	(0.56)	30°	11.0	0.9988	1522.0	2.72
-43°	3.00	1.083	280.6	(0.58)	75°	9.7	0.9931	1331.0	2.70
-40°	11.00	1.081	1406.0	(2.28)	85°	9.5	0.9922	1322.0	2.71
** -37°	14.90	1.030	2051.0	2.85	**90°	9.4	0.9913	1288.0	2.71
-32°	14.50	1.010	2032.0	2.85	100°	9.0	0.9902	1288.0	2.67
-25°	14.00	1.006	1963.0	2.84	120°	8.10	0.9880	1093.0	2.56
-20°	13.70	1.005	1921.0	2.83	160°	8.133	0.9836	1104.0	2.70
-10°	13.10	1.003	1833.0	2.82	†180°	6.133	0.9814	796.0	2.26

*Dielectric data from Yager and Morgan, *loc. cit.* Density data from White and Morgan, *loc. cit.*

**Transition point.

†Liquid.

TABLE III

Moments.

Compound.	Solvent.	μ_{new} .		μ_{DCM} .	μ_{calc} .
		1 kT.	1.5 kT.		
Camphor	Solid ^a	2.80			2.90
	Liquid ^a	(2.28)	2.79		
	Benzene ^b	2.55-2.68		2.92	
	Hexane	(2.25)	2.76	2.91	

(a) Data from Yager and Morgan, *loc. cit.* White and Morgan, *loc. cit.*

(b) Present work.

DISCUSSION

From the study of the melting point curve of dilute solutions of camphor in benzene, Parraud (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1950, 103) indicated the existence of a compound of the type $C_{10}H_{16}O:C_6H_6$. The existence of such a compound indicates the presence of an interaction between the molecules of the solute and the solvent molecules, creating a labile union between the two.

White and Morgan (*loc. cit.*) have qualitatively explained the dielectric data of solid camphor on the basis of Pauling's theory of dipole rotation. The lower apparent moment of camphor in dilute solutions has been explained on the assumption of a large value of atomic polarisation.

In the present work, the dielectric constants and densities of concentrated solutions of camphor in benzene have been measured over a range of temperature. The moment of solid and liquid camphor has been recalculated by using the data of Yager and Morgan (*loc. cit.*) and White and Morgan (*loc. cit.*).

The new moment of camphor in benzene is independent of temperature but varies with concentration. It will be seen from the graph that the limiting value of moment in hexane is in agreement with the value of liquid camphor. This indicates that dipole in camphor molecule in the liquid state is diluted by the non-polar groups to the same extent as in dilute solutions in hexane. It appears that in the liquid state and in hexane $2j+1=2$ ($1kT$) increases to $2j+1=3$ ($1.5kT$), thus increasing the moment values to 2.79 in liquid state and 2.76 in hexane.

The moment of solid camphor at low temperatures ($\sim -40^\circ$) is 2.80 which is the true moment for ketones. The moment decreases with rise of temperature and finally reaches a value of 2.25 in the liquid state. It seems that in the solid state at low temperatures, only parallel and anti-parallel orientations equivalent to $2j+1=2$, are possible. With increase in temperature, the degree of freedom of orientation increases and finally reaches a value of $2j+1=3$ ($1.5kT$) in the liquid state.

Concentrated solutions of camphor in benzene show the same degree of freedom of orientation as in the solid state at low temperatures. This is probably due to affinity of the ketone group towards the solvent. As already indicated, the melting point curves of camphor in benzene indicate the existence of a complex of the type $C_{10}H_{16}O : C_6H_6$. The dielectric polarisation study, though not able to show the existence of such a compound, does certainly indicate the possibility of such a complex formation, and thus restricting the rotation of the camphor molecule to parallel and anti-parallel orientations only.

The dipole moment of solid camphor shows that the freedom of orientation of camphor molecule increases with temperature, finally reaching a value of $2j + 1 = 3(1.5kT)$ in the liquid state. In contrast to this, the moments of hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide are the same in solid, liquid and gaseous states. This indicates that in these two molecules only parallel and anti-parallel orientations, equivalent to $2j + 1 = 2$, are possible. The difference of behaviour between camphor on one hand and hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide on the other, is due to difference in their molecular structure. The molecule of camphor has got a spherical contour and a large ratio of non-polar to polar groups, which permits of random orientation in the liquid state. This would also indicate less intermolecular binding in the case of liquid camphor. In the case of hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide, the $HCl \cdot HCl$, and $HBr \cdots HBr$ type of intermolecular binding makes it impossible for the molecules to have random orientations.

Alike camphor, borneol and isoborneol also show rotation in the solid state. However, no conclusion can be drawn in the case of these two compounds as the data available are not complete.

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Received February 15, 1959.